

THE INTERACTION PATTERNS OF INSTITUTIONAL WORKERS IN PERCEPTION OF VISION, MISSION, AND PERFORMANCE TARGETS BASED ON QMS ISO 9001:2015 AT THE UNIVERSITY OF HASANUDDIN MAKASSAR

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to describe, elaborate, and analyze the pattern of interaction (social relations) of workers institutionally in perceiving the vision, mission, and performance targets based on the ISO 9001:2015 QMS. The data and information collection methods used were observation, interviews, and or FGDs as well as a documented information system. While the analysis technique was mainly using pattern matching analysis, and explanation building.

There were seven results of this research. First, there were three patterns of social relations. Dominative social relations referred to the social position of a person or group of people in imposing their will on other people or other groups (other parties), and perhaps other parties or decision-makers accept/obey it. Social relation was equal, there is no coercion (between decision-makers). Finally, diagonal social relations sometimes had coercion in making and implementing decisions. Second, the pattern of interaction/social relations of workers institutionally in perceiving the vision, mission, and performance targets/quality targets, was generally conducive. Yet, certain cases needed to be addressed, especially with the main tasks and limits of authority between work units. Third, some patterns of interaction or social relations between workers had not been institutionally oriented. For example, there was still a lack of understanding that Unhas workers were one team and one system and one goal is to advance Unhas. The fourth, institutional forms of social relations at Unhas such as coordination, integration, and synchronization had been able to contribute to the achievement of the university's quality goals, but were not yet optimal and evenly distributed across all work units. The fifth, integration and synchronization in Unhas Management OTK Number 2 of 2022 were still lacking in its function in realizing the achievement of Unhas quality targets based on ISO 9001:2015. Sixth, the forms of social relations of workers that were built at Unhas were dominative, equal, and diagonal (there was no prominent form, so at times they were dominant, equal, and diagonal). The pattern of this relationship had not been seen which form was conducive to achieving the quality goals/performance targets of Unhas. Seventh, there was still arrogance/individual domination of fellow workers and the dominance between work units which tend to be less based on the principles of QMS ISO 9001:2015, and interfere with the achievement of Unhas quality goals and the absence of a conducive and institutionally oriented system/social relationship in perceiving the vision, mission, quality goals and objectives based on SMM ISO 9001:2015.

Keywords: interaction pattern, quality management system, ISO 9001:2015 standard, performance target.

A. Introduction

How is the pattern of interaction or social relations of workers institutionally built and perceived in the context of the vision, mission, and performance targets/quality targets of Unhas based on the ISO 9001:2015 Quality Management System (QMS)? This question is a reference for describing, elaborating, and analyzing.

This section consists of three main aspects. The first is the pattern of institutional interaction. Second, social relations are institutionalized in perceiving the goals, mission, vision, values, and working principles of Unhas. The third is the behavior of workers in achieving performance targets or quality targets based on ISO 9001:2015. Thus, the author uses three basic ideas, such as the sociological perspective, using the perspective of QMS ISO 9001:2015. And the third is regulations/policies as a rationale related to the data and information and to complement the two perspectives used.

In this regard, the pattern of institutional interaction between workers and work units is seen in the organizational structure of Unhas, Unhas Organizational Structure Based on the

Regulation of the Chancellor of Hasanuddin University Number 2/UN4.1/2022 concerning the Organization and Management of Hasanuddin University. The basic idea of Unhas' organizational structure is related to inter-unit working relationships. The working relationship is coordination, integration, and synchronization (Unhas working principle). In addition, the organizational structure of Hasanuddin University is based on the Unhas statute as a legal entity state university (PTN-BH). In this structure, there are three strategic organs, namely; the Board of Trustees (MWA), University Academic Senate (SA), and Chancellor.

The Board of Trustees (MWA) is the Unhas organ that determines, provides consideration for the implementation of general policies, and carries out supervision in the non-academic field. The Academic Senate (SA) is the Unhas organ that establishes policies, provides considerations, and conducts supervision in the academic field. The Vice-Chancellor is under and responsible to the Chancellor. The Chancellor is the Unhas organ that leads the implementation and management of Unhas.

The Rector in leading the implementation and management of Unhas is assisted by several organs or elements. It consists of (1) The Vice-Rector assists the Rector in formulating and implementing policies in the academic, planning, financial, and infrastructure fields; student affairs and alumni; and research, innovation, and partnerships. (2) The Secretary of the University is under and responsible to the Rector, and has the task of ensuring the accuracy, effectiveness, and efficiency of University management administration, ensuring the availability and accuracy of public relations information, as well as implementing policies in the field of institutions and human resources. (3) Internal Supervision Unit (SPI) organ is under and responsible to the Rector and coordinates with the Vice-Rector according to their respective fields of duty and the University Secretary. (4) The Institute for Quality Assurance and Educational Development (LPMPP), the Institute for Research and Community Service (LP2M) and this organ are under and responsible to the Rector and coordinate with the Vice-Rector according to their respective fields of duty and the University Secretary. (5) Faculties and schools are led by a dean who is under and responsible to the Rector, and has the task of organizing and managing academic education, and professional education, or can organize and manage vocational education within a clump of scientific, technological, and or artistic disciplines. (6) Directorate; (7) Academic Support; (8) Administrative Executive (Bureau, Section, and Sub Division); (9) Technical Implementation Unit (UPT), including UPT Library, UPT General Course, UPT Language Center, UPT Unhas Press, and UPT Campus Infrastructure and Utilities Management; (10) Business Management Unit; and (11) other elements required and determined by the Chancellor (see Government Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia number 53 of 2015 concerning the Statute of Hasanuddin University, and Regulation of the Chancellor of Hasanuddin University Number 2/UN4.1/2022 concerning Organization and Management of Hasanuddin University).

B. Literature review

According to Simmel (in Ritzer, 2011:31), social relations or patterns of social interaction refer to social relationships that are based on a system of values or social norms and are relatively stable. In contrast to Simmel, Dahrendorf (see Kinloch, 2005:216-217) defined

social relations as a form of relationship between members in a social entity formed by two social positions, namely the position of dominance and obedience. The pattern of interaction between workers is often a problem that is not simple in organizations. This is emphasized by Pulubuhu (2005:13) that it is important for humans or the community to have the correct and relevant knowledge and abilities in managing and controlling various problems including the need for knowledge and ability in preparing all parties to manage various problems (read: conflict management) in the organization.

In contrast to Pulubuhu, Dahrendorf (see Turner, 1991; and Kinloch, 2005:2016-2017) stated individuals and groups in organizations need to be coordinated both vertically and horizontally. Furthermore, it is emphasized that the relationship between workers is shaped by two social positions or authority structures, namely, positions of domination and obedience. Social dominance refers to the leader or decision-maker, while obedience is to subordinates or those who carry out decisions. Although Dahrendorf's central assumption explained that social change, social conflict, and coercion can occur anywhere. Thus, every element in the organization/society tends to contribute to change and especially to conflict. However, according to Dahrendorf, every group or sub-group in the organization is an element that has a spirit of order, even though it is formed by latent interests. Therefore, organizations or institutions can be seen as a set of competitive processes, groups that have a spirit of order and are assisted by interests and conditions in the organization (technical conditions, political conditions, social conditions, and psychological conditions).

Pulubuhu and Dahrendorf's thoughts can be seen in Linda Suskie's study of the importance of the quality dimension in organizations. Linda Suskie (2015) in her book *Five Dimensions of Quality: A Common Sense Guide to an Accreditation and Accountability*, defines "organizational quality" related to five dimensions, namely: (1) relevance, (2) community, (3) focus and aspirations, (4) evidence, and (5) improvement. These five dimensions determine whether an organization has a good truly good quality culture because today's quality must be spread and persisted and internalized, not a practice that was implemented in several places before the accreditation review and then forgotten. Furthermore, Suskie emphasized that accreditation/certification is one of the most poorly understood and controversial features of American higher education. Even for many academics, accreditation or certification remains a mystery. Most faculty members and many of these academic administrators have little or no direct involvement with the goals and the certification/accreditation process and view them as a mysterious, intrusive, demanding, unnecessary, and burdensome external force.

In line with Suskie's study, Goffman's idea (see Kinloch, 2005:246-247) emphasizes the existence of 3 (three) basic behaviors in organizations/associations, namely, (a) the way an individual presents in work situations; (b) the way he controls and controls the influence of others who shape him; and (c) various things he may or may not do to justify his actions in front of others.

C. Material and Method

This research used a case study research strategy. The authors conducted by observing phenomena in the real-life context of Unhas workers. It also included carefully a program, event, activity, process, or group of individuals using the interview method. Cases were limited by time and activity, and the researcher collects complete data and information by using various procedures or data collection techniques based on the allotted time.

Observation patterns were; (1) Whole participants – researchers hide their role as observers in obtaining data and information; (2) Researchers get direct experience from participants; (3) Researchers as participants – researchers demonstrate their role as observers; (4) Researchers make recordings when they need data and information; and (5) Researchers obtain personal data and information that may be reported/presented in a limited manner for discussion and analysis.

While the pattern of interviews was conducted with several approaches; (1) Face face – the researcher conducts interviews individually and primarily with key informants; (2) Telephone – the researcher interviewed the participants by telephone. Some of the informants include key informants in obtaining data and information; (3) Focus group Discussion – the researcher interviewed in a group; and (4) Internet interviews by email, Whatsapp, and online tools. To support and complete the data and information from the results of using the observation and interview methods, the researchers also used a documentation study, for example, public documents, such as annual work reports, annual strategic plans, ISO documents, books, and journals and others.

Data analysis techniques in this research were as follows; (a) social phenomenological analysis, a strategy/analysis method that places the informant as a subject who becomes a social actor in everyday life or describes the actual behavior of workers in their daily life in the world of work; (b) descriptive analysis by describing the development of the key concepts used; (c) analysis of pattern matching. This analysis was comparing patterns based on empirical facts with predicted patterns. If these two patterns had similarities, the results strengthened the internal validity of the case study in question. Pattern matching analysis in this paper is to compare the initial predictions or assumptions that will occur with the facts in the field, and (d) build an explanation (explanation building). namely a way of analyzing data by constructing an explanation of the case. The last technique was very relevant to answering the causal question "why" and helped strengthen pattern matching techniques.

D. Result and Discussion

Carrying out the functions, main tasks and authorities of workers and work units are based on four values and three working principles as important elements in the pattern of institutional interaction at Unhas. There are coordination, integration, and synchronization/harmonization. This is emphasized in the Unhas Management OTK (Organization and work procedures) Number 2 of 2022, in article 113 which emphasizes that "in carrying out its duties and functions, every head of the work unit within the Unhas environment is obliged to apply the principles of coordination, integration, and synchronization, both within the environment and

between units. work units and other agencies outside Unhas according to their respective duties. Furthermore, in Article 115, it is stated that "every head of the work unit within the Unhas is directly responsible for, leading and coordinating as well as being an example both in carrying out duties and functions as well as in providing guidance and instructions to their respective subordinates. In this regard, the statement of informant A:

“... as a leader, I always suggest to my staff to be able to serve well and quickly to anyone and especially to the leadership ... *Alhamdulillah*, my two staffs were able to show their performance, especially the speed of service ... because it is not uncommon for me to convey my experience and knowledge to my staff, this affects my staff... less than 10 minutes, the data and information I need can be served immediately...” (interview, March 29, 2022).

In connection with the statement from informant A above, it can be confirmed in three views, namely Dahrendorf, Blumer, and the ISO 9001:2015 QMS standard or principle. Dahrendorf (see Turner, 1991; and Kinloch, 2005:2016-2017) explained that each group or sub-group in the organization is an element that has a spirit of order/order, even though it is formed by latent interests. Therefore, organizations or institutions can be seen as a set of competitive processes, groups that have a spirit of order and are aided by the interests and conditions of the organization.

In contrast to the views of Dahrendorf, Blumer (see Turner, 1991; and Kinloch, 2005:242-243) stated that the complex relationship of actions related to organizations, institutions, division of tasks, frameworks of interdependent circumstances on issues - dynamic problems. Thus, the existence of workers in the organization is dynamic, and development that is not static. On the other hand, individual interactions process interpretation, and on the other hand, human behavior (read: workers) and their interaction patterns are interpreted and constructed.

Meanwhile, the case presented by informant A above is related to the principles of process approach and leadership in the ISO 9001:2015 QMS. The process Approach emphasizes that consistent and predictable results are achieved more effectively and efficiently when activities are understood and managed as interrelated processes that function as a coherent system. Furthermore, the Leadership principle refers to leaders at all levels setting unity of purpose and direction and creating conditions in which people are involved in achieving the organization's quality objectives.

In contrast to the information disclosed by informant A above, informant B stated that;

“...it is better if strategic organs such as the 'work unit'... are audited, ... because the 'work unit' has the functions, duties, and authorities related to academics... but before that, it needs assistance... in the formation of study programs and the work units that determine, among others is the 'work unit', ... there is information about the process of forming study programs for two or three years and it hasn't been completed yet, ... how about this, sir?...” (Interview March 27, 2022).

The information of informant B above is related to coordination. Coordination is intended as management activities and functions that are carried out both horizontally and vertically, especially in harmonious and integrated cooperation. The element of integration in Unhas refers to a business or activity that is unified and functional and directed in achieving the goals and objectives that have been determined and agreed upon, especially in realizing the Unhas Vision and Mission. Coordination and integration are not enough to improve system performance, but synchronization is needed. Synchronization at Unhas is related to the vision and mission of Unhas with the vision and mission of the work unit, including programs and activities of all work units, is always monitored and evaluated for alignment/synchronization with the University (see Unhas Quality Manual, 2016:7; and Hasanuddin University Chancellor Regulation Number 2/ UN4.1/2022 concerning Organization and Management of Hasanuddin University). These four values and in particular these three principles serve as the rationale for further elaborating and analyzing the interaction patterns of workers at Unhas. To achieve this goal, all work units are audited periodically, both internal audits and external audits.

Furthermore, by quoting the statements of several informants, especially informant C as follows:

“...there are two departments. One of them sent a letter to the vice-Rector and maybe to the chancellor...and for a long time...they were deemed unresponsive so they went to the university leadership...this is a mistake...according to the regulations, the faculty leader should be able to send a letter to the university leadership ...” (interview 17 March 2022).

The information above showed that some workers still lacked understanding of various regulations/policies. This condition confirms Blumer's thinking (see Turner, 1991; Outhwaite, 1991; and Kinloch, 2005), which asserts that social behavior or action continues to construct a process by which actors record, interpret, and judge to deal with their situations and workers perform organic action for himself as his participation in taking the role, thus the interaction/behavior of the worker processes interpretation.

Therefore, there are different interpretations between workers and institutional interpretations. Interpretation of workers tends to be less oriented towards achieving the organization's quality objectives. This condition is also related to the principles of QMS 9001:2015 namely, the process approach which emphasizes that consistent and predictable results are achieved more effectively and efficiently when activities are understood and managed as interrelated processes that function as a coherent system.

In another context, informant D said “... many lecturers want additional assignments... I just work, ... if the leadership responds well I will go, but if it is not responded/supported, ... yes I will think about working first and highly committed...” (interview 23 March 2022).

The statement put forward is not entirely wrong, especially when referring to Article 118 of the Regulation of the Chancellor of the Hasanuddin University Number 2/UN4.1/2022 concerning the Organization and Work Administration (OTK) of the Hasanuddin University

Manager, every head of the work unit is obliged to follow, obey the instructions and be responsible. to superiors and submit reports within the specified time.

However, workers' attitudes/behaviors are just depicted by the informant. As educators/lecturers, they should understand regulations that are more relevant to their social position. For example, the behavior of lecturers has been stipulated in PP No. 53 of 2015 concerning the Unhas statute, which confirms that lecturers are professional educators and scientists with the main task of transforming, developing, and disseminating science and technology through education, research, and community service. Information from the 7th informant is based on the principles of relationship management, process approach, and leadership in the ISO 9001:2015 QMS.

In this regard, the meaning of lecturers is sometimes faced with situations that may be a dilemma for them, for example with "additional assignments". Moreover, additional tasks are interpreted as "strategic" at the university. This condition can be seen in the information from informants E and F as follows:

"...additional assignments are sometimes contested, and often interfere with the working relationship between educators...but if I am not appointed, then I will never get/occupy additional positions/tasks, let alone participate in elections, never mind... he...he.....because all this time , if there is an additional position/task for me, ... I carry it out and commit, but often call and naive first,... thank God I don't owe you anything, sir, he...he...maybe there are also educators at our University, who consider additional tasks to be more important than their duties as a lecturer,...hopefully this isn't much, sir..." (interview, 28 and 29 March 2022).

In contrast to the information above, informant G revealed:

"...why does that Mr.... mind or not agree with this Mr... who was nominated as chairman... it seems that it is this Mr., who insists on becoming chairman... moreover according to his admission that he has conveyed to several leaders that this sir... does not meet the requirements as chairman... based on the rector's regulation... (interview, 27th March 2022).

The information above shows two things. First, "additional tasks" are not up for grabs (statements of informants E and F). Second, "additional tasks" are considered important for lecturers and tend to be contested (information from informant G) or "additional assignments" for lecturers, sometimes there are still "booster" to take them and this can affect the interaction pattern between lecturers and performance of lecturer. The pattern of worker interaction is related to social position, worker attitude, skill level, education, attitude and work ethic, discipline, motivation, perception, and working environment conditions that are conducive and can create comfort in work and achieve organizational quality goals. The "additional tasks" perceived/defined by the lecturers can be the same or different from those defined and constructed by the organization. This can be confirmed in Blumer's thinking. Blumer (see Turner, 1991:97; and Kinloch, 2005:246) provided an explanation that the actor or worker tries to maximize the various interpretations that he applies to his attitude.

In addition, this study produces three forms of social relations. Three social relations or patterns of interaction between workers at Unhas can be seen in the scheme below.

Figure/Scheme 1.2 Three Forms/Patterns of Unhas Workers' Social Relations

In the scheme above, based on research results, the authors describe the social relationship of Unhas workers. Dominative social relations refer to the social position of a person or group of people in imposing their will on other people or other groups (other parties), and perhaps other parties or decision-makers accept/obey it. In equal social relations, there is no coercion (between decision-makers). Finally, diagonal social relations sometimes have coercion in making and implementing decisions. This finding, in contrast to Dahrendorf. Dahrendorf (see Turner, 1991; and Kinloch, 2005:2016-2017) emphasizes that individuals and groups in organizations need to be coordinated both vertically and horizontally. Furthermore, it is emphasized that the relationship between workers is shaped by two social positions or authority structures, namely, positions of domination and obedience.

E. Conclusion

This study, yielded seven findings. First, there are three forms of workers' social relations, namely, dominative, equal and diagonal.. Second, the pattern of interaction/social relations of workers institutionally in perceiving the vision, mission, and performance targets/quality targets, is generally conducive. Yet, certain cases need to be addressed, especially with the main tasks and limits of authority between work units. Third, there are still patterns of interaction or social relations between workers that are not yet institutionally oriented. For example, there is still a lack of understanding that Unhas workers are one team and one system and one goal is to advance Unhas. Fourth, institutional forms of social relations at Unhas such as coordination, integration, and synchronization have been able to contribute to the achievement of the university's quality goals, but are not optimal and evenly distributed in all work units. Fifth, integration and synchronization in Unhas Management OTK Number 2

of 2022 are still lacking in its function in realizing the achievement of Unhas quality targets based on ISO 9001: 2015. Sixth, the forms of social relations of workers that are built at Unhas are dominative, equal, and diagonal (there is no prominent form, so at times they are dominant, equal, and diagonal). The pattern of this relationship has not been seen which form is conducive to achieving the quality goals/performance targets of Unhas. Seventh, there is still arrogance/individual domination of fellow workers and the dominance between work units which tend to be less based on the principles of QMS ISO 9001:2015, and interfere with the achievement of Unhas quality goals and the absence of a conducive and institutionally oriented system/social relationship in perceiving the vision, mission, quality goals and objectives based on QMS ISO 9001:2015.

The recommendations needed in relation to the findings of the study are; (1) the commitment of top management that has been oriented towards quality objectives based on ISO 9001:2015 needs to be fully supported by all work unit leaders based on clear and firm policies; (2) Unhas has met the criteria as a performance-based organization and is formally able to realize quality goals both at the institutional level and in all work units, but to make it happen in real (not just formal) it must be supported by adequate policies and resources; (3) it is necessary to develop policies that can encourage patterns of interaction/social relations between workers based on high coordination, integration and synchronization; and a policy is needed that can integrate and synergize all strategic elements and work units to realize the achievement of quality targets based on ISO 9001:2015 and requires periodic and intensive socialization of the strategy, objectives, mission, vision, values and working principles of Unhas including various policies / regulations that apply at Unhas.

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